

BRIDGING WORLD THROUGH LANGUAGE: A BILINGUAL PERSPECTIVE ON *RAZIA'S RAY OF HOPE*

Benazir Naudhani
bnaudhani@unm.edu

PhD Candidate, Language, Literacy, and Sociocultural
Studies, University of New Mexico, USA.
Assistant Professor, Department of English, Balochistan
University of Information Technology, Engineering, and
Management Sciences, Quetta, Pakistan.

I. Introduction

Razia's ray of hope is a story of hope of a young girl in Afghanistan. This is a true story based on real characters. It is based on Zabuli Education Center for girls in Kabul, Afghanistan, which is founded by Razia Jan. Who left Afghanistan and went to America amidst war but then after some years she came back to Afghanistan and opened a girl's school in Afghanistan. In the story, she appears as a character of a school administrator with her real-life character and name. The school gives opportunities to village girls to study different subjects. Elizabeth Suneby is the author of *Razia's Ray of Hope*. She writes magazine articles and content for big and small companies. *Razia's Ray of Hope* is inspired by real-life Razia Jan, who founded a girl's school in Afghanistan to provide education to the girls of Afghanistan. This is an award-winning book based on the true story of a little girl in Afghanistan, who has given the fictional name Razia, she wanted to go to school, and how she convinced her male family members to give her permission to join the school (Suneby, 2020).

Figure 1

Note: Taken from *Razia's Ray of Hope* (p. 8) by Suneby, 2020, Kids Can Press.

This is a story of a young girl named Razia and her dream of getting an education. She had a dream of going to school like her brothers Karim and Jamil in her small village in Afghanistan. Whenever her brother studies she silently sits with them and gained a lot of education through her secret literacy. Hence, when she came to know that a new girls' school is being built in her village near her home, her dream seemed come true, and she was filled with hopes of getting an education from there. But her eldest brother Aziz, who

was not educated, stood against her education. Her grandfather was her only ray of hope to convince her brothers and father, but he too failed to convince them. She even goes to ask for help from Razia Jan who was a school administrator to convenience her family. But Razia Jan too failed to persuade her family. Nonetheless, young Razia proved to Aziz that education is useful when she uses her secret literacy to give him the correct dose of medicine when he falls ill. And finally, Aziz was convinced that educating Razia would benefit their family and community and agreed to send her to school.

2.Linguistic Representation

Dari-English bilingualism is represented in this book. Dari is the language spoken in Afghanistan. Dari language vocabulary integration in English narration along.

However, the English language is used more in this book as compared to the Dari language. The entire book is written in English just some vocabulary items are used in the Dari language to relate it to the context of Afghanistan. While reading this book it's quite clear that the English language has given more preference in this book as compared to the Dari language and it is written for the English-speaking audience rather than Dari/Pashto speaking audience. Although the book is written in the context of Afghanistan and based on the story of the Afghani people, their language is neglected altogether.

As English is the language of power therefore it has given more room in the story in the Afghani context rather than the Dari/Pashto language which are the actual languages of Afghanistan. As De Jong (2011) explained that many languages are losing its importance and position in the society due to the dominant status of English. Its high status has become a threat to the survival of many other languages and their cultures in society.

List of Dari Words from the Text (All of these are Dari/Pashto words some are used in Arabic as well).

Agha jan: a title of respect for elder

Baba: Father

Baba gi: Grandfather

Bibi: Mother

Burqa: Muslim women wear a wrap usually made up of cloth to cover their face and overall body in public.

Dari: One of the official languages spoken in Afghanistan.

Deh'Subz: It is a mountainous village at 48 km outside of Afghanistan's capital city, Kabul.

Jerga: a meeting held by eldest men of the family to make decisions.

Maulim sahiba: Respected teacher

Naan: A traditional flat bread eaten in Afghanistan, Pakistan, and India.

Nowruz: The Persian New year (beginning of Spring)

Pashto: One of the official languages spoken in Afghanistan.

Salam-alekum: Means “hello” and “peace”.

Tandoor: a clay oven used for cooking naan and food.

3. Illustrations from the Book

This book is written in the context of Afghanistan. The entire book is in English language, but the author has added some lexical items from the Dari language in the book to give it a taste of Afghanistan's context. Some illustrations of bilingualism are found in the book.

Extract 1

“But what is happening today? I asked. The **Nowruz** celebrations are over” (p. 4).
Nowruz is the Persian New year, which also marks the beginning of Spring.

Extract 2

“Whenever I found **Baba gi** alone, I would whisper in his ear, ‘Have you spoken to **Baba** and Aziz yet?’” (p. 7)

In this line the word **baba gi** refers to grandfather and word **baba** refers to father

Extract 3

“**Baba gi** started the **jerga**. ‘Razia wants to attend the new girls’ school in the village. I support her desire’” (p. 11).

In this sentence the word “**jerga**” is a Dari word. It means a decision-making meeting held by the eldest men in the family.

Extract 4

“From under my pillow, I took out scraps of newspaper that the baker wrapped around our freshly baked **naan**” (p. 16).

In this extract the word **naan** is taken from Dari language it means bread.

Extract 5

“**Baba gi**, the **maulim sahiba** from the new girls’ school is here to speak to you! Please come greet her. Bring **Baba** and **Bibi**. I spoke a mile a minute so as not to waste any time.

In these lines “word **baba gi**” is taken from Dari language and word “**maulim sahiba**” is also taken from Dari language which mean ‘respected teacher’ (p.17).

Figure 2

Note: Taken from *Razia's Ray of Hope* (p. 14) by Suneby, 2020, Kids Can Press.

Extract 6

“I leapt up and threw my arms around Aziz. I promise to stay clear of danger. Thank you **Agha jan**” (p. 20).

In these lines Razia thanked her brother. “Agha jan” in Dari language refers to elder brother.

Figure 3

Note: Taken from *Razia's Ray of Hope* (p. 12) by Suneby, 2020, Kids Can Press.

Secondly, I appreciate the way culture is represented through pictorial illustrations in the book is a real depiction of Afghani culture and tradition by a foreign author. Boys and men are wearing kameez shalwar (traditional Afghani outfit) with topi (hat). Men are seen wearing (patkay) turbans and waistcoats. Girls and women are wearing kameez shalwar (traditional Afghani outfit for women) with dopata (scarf) to cover their heads. Females are also seen wearing burqa (outfit to cover their head to toe). But even then, it does not reflect the dress of most Afghani's today. People and their clothing have changed.

4. Book Interpretation and its Relevance to the Bilingual context

It was the story of little girl Razia who wished to go to a girls' school, that was built in her neighborhood, to get an education. In this paper the book is analyzed in the context of bilingualism. Because it is written in both English and Dari language. But it

seems that the writer used English language more than Dari in the book. Only a few words of the Dari language have been used in the book. But the way the writer has embedded two languages in the book very beautifully giving the context of Kabul to its readers. However, the book clearly represents the power of English on the Dari language. The writer has given more focus to English than Dari.

How two languages (Dari and English) are used in this book. Although, the entire book is in the English language the author has used code-switching by adding Dari words in it. When a bilingual person starts a conversation in one language and then switches to other language by adding words and phrases from other language is referred as codeswitching (de Jong, 2011)

When something relates to our language and culture, we take more interest in that content. It would be very easy for me to associate this book's language with my student's mother tongue and culture. As Nelson Mandela said, "If you talk to a man in a language he understands, that goes to his head. If you talk to him in his language, that goes to his heart".

5. Book Critique and Conclusion

This book is written in the context of Afghanistan and the Afghan people, but this book does not relate much to Dari speaking people. This book is written more for English speaking audience than the Afghani audience. Because the book is entirely written in the English language and very few words are taken from the Afghani language i.e, Dari. As the book does not use Dari language that is one of the languages in Afghanistan, it is quite hard for the teacher to teach this book in a bilingual classroom for Afghani students. As de Jong (2011) explained identity can also be represented through clothes, food, and musing but language is an important part of one's identity and culture.

References

- De Jong, E. J. (2011). *Foundations for multilingualism in education: From principles to practice*. Caslon Publishing.
- Grosjean, F. (1985). The bilingual as a competent but specific speaker-hearer. *Journal of Multilingual and Multicultural Development*, 6(6), 467-477.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/01434632.1985.9994221>
- Skutnabb-Kangas, T. (1995). Multilingualism and the education of minority children. *Estudios Fronterizos*, (18-19), 36-67.
<https://doi.org/10.21670/ref.1989.18-19.a02>
- Suneby, E. (2022, February 20). *Elizabeth Suneby- Author*. Kids Can Press.
<https://www.kidscanpress.com/creators/elizabeth-suneby/802>
- Suneby, E. (2020). *Razia's ray of hope: One girl's dream of an education*. Kids Can Press.